

ANTIMICROBIAL AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF *COLEUS ANTHONYI* (LAMIACEAE)

*A.Tamil Selvan, Ancy.G¹, Keziya R. Rasalan², Alfiya.S³, Anju Santhosh⁴, Asna.A⁵

¹⁻⁵Department of Pharmacology

Kerala Academy of Pharmacy, Kandala, Near Kattakada,

Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala – 695572.

Abstract

Lamiaceae, also known as Mint family, is a large and diverse family of wide aromatic flowering plants with global distribution, including many culinary, medicinal and ornamental species. The aim of the present study is to explore the antimicrobial and antioxidant properties of *Coleus anthonyi* belongs to Lamiaceae family. Hydroethanolic extract of whole plant was chosen to screen against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus mutans*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, the results were significant measured by the zone of inhibition compared with the standard Streptomycin 100mcg. Antioxidant assays were done by DPPH and NO methods using Ascorbic acid and Gallic acid as Positive Control. Preliminary phytoconstituent evaluation revealed the presence of Flavonoids, Terpenoids and Tannins were responsible for the desired biological effects. Further studies are going on to reveal the possible mechanisms and phytochemical nature.

Keywords: *Coleus anthonyi*, Lamiaceae, Hydroethanolic extract, Flavonoids, Terpenoids, Tannins, anti-bacterial activity, Streptomycin, anti-oxidant property, Ascorbic acid and Gallic acid.

Introduction

Each year, over 13 million deaths worldwide are attributed to the emergence of new infectious diseases or the re-emergence of previously controlled pathogens¹. Bacterial infections pose a significant threat to public health, as many pathogenic bacteria quickly develop resistance to multiple antibiotics². Traditionally, medicinal plants have been used across the globe for various therapeutic purposes, including the treatment of microbial diseases³. Indeed, the ability of plant extracts to inhibit the growth of pathogenic bacteria has become a focus of recent research, particularly for their potential to modulate bacterial drug resistance. These studies could serve as a valuable reference for guiding future research aimed at reversing microbial resistance⁴. According to the literature, thousands of plant species have been tested in vitro against many bacterial strains, and a good number of medicinal plant extracts and pure compounds have now been proven to be active against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria⁵. In traditional medicine, plant extracts with MIC values below 8 mg/mL are considered active⁶.

***Coleus anthonyi* (Lamiaceae): A New Species from South Western Ghats, India**

A new species of *Coleus* (Lamiaceae: Ocimeae: Plectranthinae), *C. anthonyi*, from the South Western Ghats region of India is described. Detailed taxonomic description, colour photographs, illustration, status and key to the allied species of the new taxon are provided. *Coleus loureiroi* is an old world tropical distributed genus having more than 450 species (Paton *et al.*, 2018)⁷. Recent phylogenetical and nomenclature studies on Subtribe Plectranthinae have resulted in the generic delimitation and inclusion of *Anisochilus Wallich* ex Benth to *Coleus* (Paton *et al.*, 2018; 2019)⁸. This genus consists of annual or perennial herbs or shrubs and can be recognized by its 5 lobed calyx (1 upper, 4 lower) with pedicel attached asymmetrically to the base of calyx tube, opposite the posterior lip and usually, corolla with upper lip shorter than lower. The genus occurs in montane forests, shola and grasslands of Western Ghats are the probable centre of distribution of *Coleus*. Recent discoveries viz., *C. achankoviliensis*, *C. anamudianus*, *C. idukkianus*; *C. kanyakumariensis*, *C. petricola*, *C. saxorum* and *C. shoolamudianus* from this area require intensive taxonomic and explorative studies of the genus. (Paton *et al.* 2019)⁹. Botanical exploration of Thiruvananthapuram District of south Western Ghats, during 2018–2019, yielded some interesting specimens of the genus *Coleus* (subgenus *Anisochilus*). Critical analysis of the literature (Gamble, 1924; Sasidharan, 2013;

Smitha, 2017)¹⁰, recent scientific papers (Paton *et al.*, 2019; Mathew *et al.*, 2017a; b; Smitha & Sunojkumar, 2018)¹¹ as well as of herbarium specimens availed at MH, CAL, TBGT and CUBH revealed that these collected specimens do not match any of the previously described species and here it is described as a new species. The present study was aimed to evaluate the antibacterial activity of *Coleus anthonyi* (Lamiaceae) Whole plant and to explore its antioxidant property.

Materials and Methods

Collection of Plant Materials

Fresh Whole plant of *Coleus anthonyi* (Lamiaceae) were collected from the local regions of Thiruvananthapuram. The plant was washed with tap water and shade dried. The plant specimen was identified and authenticated by KSCSTE – Jawaharlal Nehru Tropical Botanic Garden and Research Institute (An Institution of Kerala State Council for Science, Technology & Environment), Karimancode, Pacha-Palode, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India and Collection. No: TBGT 108363, Date of collection 12.12.2025. After shade drying, the plants were coarsely powdered and the powder was subjected to various studies for which the materials and methods presented below.

Extraction of Plant Materials

Weighed coarse powder used for the extraction by successive solvent extraction by Soxhlet apparatus using various solvents. Petroleum ether extract About 500gm of coarse powder was extracted with 2.5 litre of petroleum ether (60-80°C) by continuous hot percolation using Soxhlet apparatus¹². The extraction was continued up to 24hours. After completion, the petroleum ether extract was filtered and solvent removed by distillation under reduced pressure. Then, the obtained residue was stored in a desiccator. Hydroalcoholic (Ethanol 95% w/w) extract Marc obtained from the above extract was dried, extracted with hydroalcoholic mixture of ethanol and water in the ratio of 70:30 (79 - 81°C) by using Soxhlet apparatus. The extraction was continued up to 24 hours. After completion of extraction, the solvent was filtered and removed by distillation under reduced pressure. Then it was stored in desiccator, freeze dried and used for the study¹³. From the weight of each extractive residue, the extractive values were calculated in percentage¹⁴. All the above extracts were used for identification of constituents by preliminary phytochemical tests, hydroalcoholic extract reported to have flavonoids as the result of preliminary phytochemical screening.

Identification of Phytoconstituents by Qualitative Chemical Tests

The petroleum ether and hydro alcoholic extracts of *Coleus anthonyi* was subjected to phytochemical analysis for identification of plant constituents by chemical tests¹⁵.

Antibacterial Screening (Agar- Well Diffusion Method)

Petri plates containing 20ml Muller Hinton Agar Medium were seeded with bacterial culture of *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus mutans*. (growth of culture adjusted according to McFarland Standard, 0.5%). Wells of approximately 10mm was bored using a well cutter and different concentrations of sample such as 250µg, 500µg and 1000µg were added. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The antibacterial activity was assayed by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around the well (NCCLS, 1993)¹⁶. Streptomycin was used as a positive control.

Antioxidant Assays

DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The radical scavenging activity of different extracts was determined by using DPPH assay according to Chang *et al* [2001]¹⁷. The decrease in the absorption of the DPPH solution after the addition of an antioxidant was measured at 517 nm. Different concentrations of sample such as 12.5µg/mL- 200µg/mL from stock solution of 10 mg/mL were made up to a final volume of 20µl with DMSO were taken and 1.48ml DPPH (0.1mM) solution was added. A control without the test compound, but an equivalent amount of distilled water was taken. The reaction mixture incubated in dark condition at room temperature for 20 minutes. After 20 minutes, the absorbance of the mixture was read at 517nm (SHIMADZU(UV-1900i) UV-VIS spectrophotometer). 3ml of DPPH was taken as control.

Nitric Oxide Scavenging Activity

1.5mL of Sodium nitroprusside (5mmolL⁻¹ - dissolved in phosphate buffered saline pH 7.4), was mixed with different concentration of sample such as 125µg/mL -2000µg/mL from a stock concentration of 10mg/mL and incubated at 25°C for 60minutes. A control without the test compound, but an equivalent amount of distilled water was taken. After 60minutes, 1.5mL of the incubated solution was removed and diluted with 1.5mL of Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide, 2% phosphoric acid and 0.1% N-1-naphthyl ethylene diaminedihydrochloride).

Absorbance of the chromophore formed during diazotization of the nitrate with sulphanilamide and subsequent coupling with N-1 naphthyl ethylene diaminedihydrochloride was measured at 546nm using a UV-Visible-light spectrophotometer (SHIMADZU – UV - 1900i) and the percentage scavenging activity was measured with reference to the standard gallic acid¹⁸.

Results and Discussion

Name of the Plant, Part Used and Its Pharmacological Evaluation

Name of the Plant	Part used	Pharmacological evaluation
<i>Coleus anthonyi</i>	Whole plant	Antibacterial and Antioxidant activity

Extractive Values

From the weight of each extractive residue, the extractive values were calculated in percentage. All the extracts were used for identification of constituents by phytochemical tests. The extractive value indicates the yield of the extract obtained from the air-dried plant powder by successive solvent extraction by Soxhlet extraction. Their percentage yield shows the solubility of the active principles in the organic solvents used based upon the polarity nature. They are then identified and confirmed by the preliminary phytochemical evaluation.

Extraction of Air-Dried Whole Plant of *Coleus anthonyi* (L)

Method of Extraction	Solvents	Colour	Consistency	Average value of extractive (%W/W)
Continuous Hot percolation by Soxhlet apparatus	Petroleum ether (60 - 80°C)	Light Green	Semisolid	2.07g (4.03)
	Hydroethanolic (95%) Distilled water (70): Ethanol (30)	Dark brown	Paste	22.74g (6.83)

Qualitative Analysis of the Crude Extracts of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant

Name of the Test	Petroleum ether extract	Hydro alcoholic extract
Carbohydrates	+	-
Reducing sugar	-	-
Proteins	-	+
Amino acids	-	+
Saponification	-	-
Cardiac glycosides	-	+
Anthraquinone glycosides	+	+
Saponins	-	+
Flavonoids	+	++
Alkaloids	-	+
Tannins and Phenolics	-	++
Steroids	+	-
Enzymes	-	-

(-) – Absent, (+) – Present

Hydroethanolic extract showed significant antibacterial activity, the results were calculated by means of zone of inhibition by the extract and compared with that of the standard. The main phyto ingredient was flavonoids were responsible for the above-mentioned biological response.

Invitro Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Staphylococcus aureus*

Sample code	Concentration(μg)	Zone of inhibition n(mm)
Streptomycin	100	24
<i>Coleus anthonyi</i>	250	18
	500	21
	1000	23

Invitro Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Staphylococcus aureus* – Zone of Inhibition

Invitro Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Streptococcus mutans*

Sample code	Concentration(μg)	Zone of inhibition (mm)
Streptomycin	100	23
<i>Coleus anthonyi</i>	250	15
	500	19
	1000	23

***In vitro* Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Streptococcus mutans* – Zone of Inhibition**

Sample code	Concentration (μg)	Zone of inhibition (mm)
-------------	---------------------------------	-------------------------

Streptomycin	100	28
<i>Coleus anthonyi</i>	250	Nil
	500	11
	1000	14

Invitro* Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Escherichia coli

***Invitro* Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Escherichia coli* - Zone of inhibition**

In vitro* Antibacterial activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa

Sample code	Concentration(μg)	Zone of inhibition(mm)
Streptomycin	100	27
<i>Coleus anthonyi</i>	250	Nil
	500	Nil
	1000	15

***In vitro* Antibacterial Activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* - Zone of inhibition**

***In vitro* Antioxidant activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant by DPPH Method**

Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance	Percentage of inhibition
Control	0.556	0.0000
12.5	0.393	29.3165
25	0.339	39.0288
50	0.264	52.5180
100	0.125	77.5180
200	0.072	87.0504

IC 50 Value - *COLEUS ANTHONYI*: 45.1565 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Calculated using ED 50 PLUS V1.0 Software)

(Graphical representation of DPPH Radical scavenging assay in *COLEUS ANTHONYI*. Along Y axis, Percentage of inhibition (%). Along X axis, Concentration of *COLEUS ANTHONYI* ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)

***Invitro* Antioxidant activity of Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Coleus anthonyi* (L) Whole Plant by Nitric Oxide Method**

Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance	Percentage of inhibition
Control	0.420	0.000
125	0.316	24.762
250	0.284	32.381
500	0.204	51.429
1000	0.165	60.714
2000	0.085	79.762

IC 50 Value - *COLEUS ANTHONYI*:483.896 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (Calculated using ED 50 PLUS V1.0 Software)

Graphical representation depicting the Nitric oxide scavenging activity of *COLEUS ANTHONYI*. Along Y axis Percentage inhibition, Along X axis varied concentration of *COLEUS ANTHONYI*.

Summary and Conclusion

Concerns over the sustainability of human life are making it more and more important to resist the harmful effects of microbes. Numerous microbes coexist in biological harmony with the human body and its environs, but unchecked or fast microbial growth can cause some potentially harmful issues. Antimicrobial medications are used to prevent infections in human body, nevertheless they have a variety of negative side effects, particularly if they raise reactive oxygen species levels in the human body¹⁹. Numerous plant species are among the herbal substances utilized as therapeutic plants. Many studies have recently been conducted to examine antimicrobial activities in response to rising public concern about hygiene. Antimicrobial agents have potentially harmful or hazardous effects, hence their usage needs to be monitored. In the past few years, because of older antibiotics' fewer negative reactions are being experienced, as more people are choosing to use natural substances rather than synthetic or chemical medicines²⁰, herbal plants are used as medicines. Plants can be utilized directly as their active ingredients or as plant extracts. The majority of the world's inhabitants also use herbal remedies because of their potent antibacterial effects and advantages for basic healthcare. Furthermore, oxidative stress slows down the cellular processes required for wound healing and increases the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS)²¹. Biomaterials with strong antibacterial activity, like herbal plant medicine, can take the role of antibiotics. The antimicrobial qualities particular of plants are highlighted in this review paper. This review discusses the recent progress on antimicrobial properties of herbal materials and their efficacy in eradicating bacteria and fungus²². Based on the literature survey and analysis, the plant *Coleus anthonyi* was chosen for antimicrobial and antioxidant property evaluation. The whole plant was chosen for the study as it contains various secondary metabolites and phytoingredients present in all parts of the plant²³. The solvents were chosen upon the polarity nature of the secondary metabolites' dissolves in the particular solvent. The hydroethanolic extract yield was chosen as it contains more phytoconstituents mainly focused on phenolics and flavonoids. That was confirmed with the preliminary phytochemical evaluation. Presence of those phytocompounds were the reason for the particular anti-bacterial and antioxidant activities.

Acknowledgement

The author (s) were thankful to The Chairman, The Head, HR & Recruitment, The Principal, Kerala Academy of Pharmacy, Thiruvananthapuram for their financial support and timely help to make this research a successful one. There is no conflict of interest in publishing this research work.

References

1. Barik, S. K., Haridasan, K., Lakadong, N. J., 2007. Medicinal Plant Resources of Meghalaya: Endemism, Threat Status and Consumption Pattern, In: *Envis Forestry Bulletin*, 7(2).
2. Borthakur, S. K., 1996. Wild Edible Plants in Markets of Assam, India. An Ethnobotanical Investigation. In: *Ethnobiology in Human Welfare*, Deep Publication, New Delhi, pp. 31-34.
3. Jain, S. K., 1991. In: *Dictionary of Indian Folk Medicine and Ethnobotany*.
4. Kanjilal, U. N., 1997. In: *The Flora of Assam*, Omsons Publications, New Delhi-110027, I(I), p. 93.
5. Khanikar, G., 2008. In: *Uttam banaushadhi*, 3rd ed., published by Astha Prakashan, Zoo road Tiniali, Guwahati-24, Assam, p.18.
6. Khare, C. P., 2007. In: *Indian Medicinal Plants, An Illustrated Dictionary*, publisher: Springer Science plus Business Media, LLC., 233, Spring Street, New York, NY 10013, USA. p. 367.
7. Phukan B., Kakati B.B., and Kumar. A., "In vitro anthelmintic activity of *Justicia gendarusa* linn." *Microbiology, Asian Journal Biotechnology of and Environmental Sciences*, VOL. 15, NO. 4, 2013. 725-728 (ISSN-0972-3005).
8. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) guidelines for acute toxicity of Chemicals. No 425 (Adopted: 3 October 2008), Available at: www.Oecd.org.chs.
9. Schurr, P. E., Schultz, J. R., Parkinson, T. M., 1972. Triton induced hyperlipidemia in rats as an animal model for screening hypolipidemic drugs, *Lipids*, 7, 69.
10. Swapnil, S. K., Deshbandhu, R. P., Swapnil, D. M., 2011. An acute oral toxicity study *Gnidiaglauca* (Fresen.) Gilg. In Albino rats as per OECD Guideline 425, *Int J Pharm Tech Res*. 3.
11. Gamble JS, 1924. Labiatae, *Flora of the Presidency of Madras* 2(6): 1106–1159. Adlard & Son & West Newman, London.
12. Mathew J, Yohannan R, Conn BJ, 2017a. Three new species Mathew J, Yohannan R, Conn BJ, 2017a. Three new species of *Plectranthus* L'Hér. (Lamiaceae) from south Western Ghats, India. *Telopea*, 20: 179–191.
13. Mathew J, Yohannan R, George KV, 2017b. *Anisochilus petraeus* (Lamiaceae), a new species from Southern Western Ghats, India. *Taiwania*, 62(2): 144–146.

14. Paton AJ, Mwanyambo M, Culham A, 2018. Phylogenetic study of *Plectranthus*, *Coleus* and allies (Lamiaceae): Taxonomy, distribution and medicinal use. Bot. J. Linn. Soc., 188(4): 355–376.
15. Paton AJ, Mwanyambo M, Rafaël HAG, Smitha K, Suddee S, Phillipson PB, Wilson TC, Forster PI, Culham A, 2019. Nomenclatural changes in *Coleus* and *Plectranthus* (Lamiaceae): a tale of more than two genera. PhytoKeys, 129: 1–158.
16. Sasidharan N, 2013. Flowering plants of Kerala: CD-ROM- Ver. 2.0. Kerala Forest Research Institute, Kerala, India.
17. Smitha K, 2017. Taxonomic revision and molecular phylogeny of the genus *Plectranthus* (Lamiaceae). PhD thesis submitted to University of Calicut, Kerala. 302 pp.
18. Smitha K, Sunojkumar P, 2018. *Plectranthus gamblei* (Lamiaceae) sp. nov. from India and notes on the identity and lectotypification of *P. bourneae*. Nordic Journal of Botany, 36(8): e01639.
19. J.K. Borchardt, The beginnings of drug therapy: Ancient mesopotamian medicine, Drug News Perspect. 15 (2002) 187–192.
20. K.C. Huang, The pharmacology of chinese herbs, 2nd ed. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1999.
21. L.D. Kapoor, CRC handbook of ayurvedic medicinal plants, CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1990.
22. S. Dev, Ancient-modern concordance in ayurvedic plants: Some examples, Environ.Health Perspect. 107 (1999) 783–789.
23. D.E. Moerman, Medicinal plants of native America, University of Michigan Museum of Anthropology, Ann Arbor, MI, 1986.
24. T. Johnson, CRC ethnobotany desk reference, CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1999.
25. N.R. Farnsworth, R.O. Akerele, A.S. Bingel, D.D. Soejarto, Z. Guo, Medicinal plants in therapy, Bull. World Health Organ. 63 (1985) 965–981.